

Liquid membrane phenomena : Effect of aspirin on cholesterol liquid membranes

Abhay K. Jain* and Manish Srivastava

Department of Chemistry, D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur-273 009, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : dr.abhay.k.jain@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 24 January 2014, revised 16 August 2014, accepted 16 August 2014

Abstract : Electroosmotic transport of water through liquid membranes generated by cholesterol in presence of aspirin (acetyl salicylic acid) has been reported. The values of the resistance coefficients have been evaluated from the transport data obtained from electroosmotic transport experiments. Attempt has been made to estimate the resistance coefficients corresponding to the liquid membranes alone in two situations : one in which the liquid membranes were generated on one side of the supporting membrane interface and other in which the liquid membranes were generated on both sides of the supporting membrane interface. It has been observed that the resistance coefficients corresponding to liquid membranes alone in presence of aspirin decrease with increase in concentration of aspirin (1 mM to 5 mM), confirming the flow of water increases. The values of degree of coupling 'q', which describe tightness of the coupling between flow of matter and electricity, have also been estimated. The results indicate that the coupling does not change appreciably as the concentration of aspirin reaches ≈ 3 mM.

Keywords : Electroosmosis, liquid membranes, lipid membranes, cholesterol, aspirin, drug action.

Introduction

The spontaneous orientation of the surfactant molecules at interface leads to the reduction of interfacial energy and is of fundamental importance in the formation of the molecular aggregates and thin films which persist in liquid state¹. Thus liquid membranes form spontaneously even without impingement as result of surfactant capacity of dissolved molecules². The surface activity is related to hydrophobic/hydrophilic balance of these molecules^{1,2}.

Cholesterol which is an important constituent of biological membranes though slightly soluble in water has been shown to lower the surface tension of water. Because of the surface active nature of cholesterol³ it is natural to expect that in the liquid membranes generated by cholesterol, the hydrophobic end of these molecules will be preferentially oriented towards the supporting membrane and hydrophilic end will be drawn outwards away from the supporting membrane³. Liquid membranes generated in this way form composite structure with the supporting membrane with which they act in series⁴⁻⁶.

The cholesterol membranes generated in this fashion

have been used to demonstrate activity of various drugs⁷. Cholesterol is one of the essential constituent of platelets, which are cytoplasmic fragments. Platelets clumping are relevant for physiology of hemostasis. Platelets is the center where blood coagulation begins. The main contribution of platelets to the clotting process seems to be lipids among many other factors⁸. High cholesterol concentration (200 mg/dl) causes the coronary artery disease (CAD) and unstable angina and acute myocardial infarction (MI)⁸. For primary prevention of these diseases, the recommended treatment includes aspirin among many other drugs⁹.

In the present communication it is intended to report effect of aspirin on flow properties of liquid membranes generated by cholesterol. For this we report electroosmosis of water through liquid membranes generated by cholesterol in presence of aspirin. The transport data have been analyzed in the light of thermodynamics of irreversible process⁹⁻¹¹ with a view to evaluate the transport coefficients corresponding to liquid membranes. The analysis of the data indicates that permeability properties of liquid membranes are changed in presence of aspirin.

Aspirin which is a non-steroidal, anti-inflammatory

and anti-coagulant drug used in treatment of patients suffering from coronary arterial disease (CAD), coronary heart disease (CHD) and cancer^{12,13}, the studies reported herein appear pertinent. Moreover, cholesterol is one of the major lipid components of plasma membrane of mammalian cell that is not oxidized as a source of energy. There has been a long interest in the role of cholesterol in determining the physical properties of cholesterol and its relationship to biological function^{14,15}.

Theory and expression :

The explicit phenomenological relations for the simultaneous transport of matter and electricity as obtained from the thermodynamics of irreversible processes in linear range can be written as⁹⁻¹¹;

$$J_v = L_{11}\Delta P + L_{12}\Delta\Phi \quad (1)$$

$$I = L_{21}\Delta P + L_{22}\Delta\Phi \quad (2)$$

which follow from following dissipation equation,

$$T \text{ dis}/dt = J_v\Delta P + I\Delta\Phi \quad (3)$$

In eqs. (1), (2) and (3), J_v and I represent volume flow and flow of electricity in presence of both pressure difference ΔP and electrical potential difference $\Delta\Phi$ respectively. The coefficients L_{ik} are called phenomenological coefficients. In view of Onsager's reciprocal relation (ORR), we have

$$L_{ik} = L_{ki} \text{ or in the present case; } L_{12} = L_{21} \quad (4)$$

In dealing with composite series membrane it is more convenient to utilize inverse phenomenological relations between thermodynamic fluxes and forces¹⁰. Based on the formalism developed by Kedem and Katchalsky¹⁶ for the composite membrane, we can write the relationship between the coefficient representing the series membrane as a whole and those of its constituent membrane elements as

$$R_{ik}^T = \sum_r R_{ik}^r \quad (5)$$

In eq. (5) subscripts T and r stand for total series membrane and the r -th membrane element respectively. The eq. (5) will be used to evaluate the transport characteristics of the liquid membranes alone generated by cholesterol in the present case.

Here the resistance coefficients (R_{ik}) are connected to the coefficient (L_{ik}) by eq. (6)

$$R_{ik} = A_{ik}/[L] \quad (6)$$

In eq. (6) A_{ik} being the minor of L_{ik} and $|L|$ the determinant of L_{ik} . Since for a symmetrical matrix L_{ik} the complements A_{ik} are symmetrical too, the R_{ik} obeys the ORR.

$$R_{ik} = R_{ki} \quad (7)$$

Experimental

Cholesterol (Sigma) was recrystallized from absolute alcohol before use in order to avoid the formation of black films¹⁷. Aspirin (Sigma) was used without further purification. Ethanol used in present experiments was purified by the method described in literature¹⁸. Distilled water distilled twice over potassium permanganate was used for preparation of aqueous solutions of cholesterol and aspirin. Cholesterol solutions were prepared by the method already described in our earlier publications^{5,6}.

An all glass transport cell described by Jain and Srivastava⁵ has been used. The sintered glass membrane (porosity G4) of thickness 2.43×10^{-3} m and area 7.74×10^{-4} m², which in fact acted as support to liquid membrane, divided the transport cell in two compartments, say side I and side II⁵. For the measurements of hydraulic permeability, electroosmotic velocity, streaming potential and streaming current, the two halves (side I and side II) of the transport cell were filled with solution of desired concentration. In the present case two types of liquid membranes have been generated : one in which liquid membranes were generated on one side (I) of the supporting membrane interface and other side (II) was filled with water {say situation (i)} and other in which the supporting liquid membrane was sandwiched between solutions of same concentration {say situation (ii)}.

The procedure followed for the measurements was similar to one described earlier^{5,6}. The volume flow was measured by noting rate of advancement of the liquid meniscus in the capillary of length 0.2 m and radius 1.042×10^{-3} m with the help of cathetometer, least count 1×10^{-5} m and stop watch reading to 0.01 s. The streaming potential was measured by using digital multimeter (Scientific measurement technique, India, model SM 5015) reading to minimum 1×10^{-5} V. The electrical potentials needed for electroosmotic velocity were maintained through a power supply (Toshniwal, India). The pressure difference was applied by a pressure head. The temperature of all measurement was kept constant to 37 ± 0.1 °C.

Results and discussion

From eqs. (1) and (2), following equalities can be arrived at :

For ordinary permeability data

$$(J_v)_{\Delta\Phi=0} = L_{11}\Delta P \quad (8)$$

For electroosmotic velocity

$$(J_v)_{\Delta P=0} = L_{12}\Delta\Phi \quad (9)$$

For streaming potential

$$(\Delta\Phi/\Delta P)_{I=0} = -L_{21}/L_{22} \quad (10)$$

For streaming current

$$(I)_{\Delta\Phi=0} = L_{21}\Delta P \quad (11)$$

All above relations predict straight line plots between fluxes and forces, passing through the origin. The values of various phenomenological coefficients L_{11} , L_{12} , L_{21} and L_{22} for pure water, cholesterol solution at concentration 30 nM (CMC) and at different concentration of aspirin ranging from 1 mM to 5 mM in cholesterol solution at CMC were calculated from slopes of such linear plots and are recorded in Table 1 for situation (i) and in Table 2 for situation (ii). The validity of ORR is obvious from Tables 1 and 2. The value of R_{11} , R_{12} , R_{21} and R_{22} estimated from eq. (6) are recorded in Table 3 for situation (i) and in Table 4 for situation (ii). The validity of eq. (7) can be seen from Tables 3 and 4.

In the present experimental studies, two types of series membranes can be visualized : the situation (i) in which membranes were generated on one side of the supporting membrane and situation (ii) in which supporting membrane was sandwiched between liquid membranes. Evidently, in situation (i) we consider two membrane el-

Table 1. Values of various phenomenological coefficients in situation (i) for different concentrations of aspirin

	$L_{11} \times 10^{12}$ ($m^5 N^{-1} s^{-1}$)	$L_{12} \times 10^{10}$ ($m^3 A J^{-1}$)	$L_{21} \times 10^{10}$ ($m^3 A J^{-1}$)	$L_{22} \times 10^4$ ($A V^{-1}$)
Pure water	1.355	2.750	2.750	0.268
30 nM (cholesterol)	0.822	0.846	0.841	0.129
1 mM ^a	0.890	1.145	1.146	0.162
2 mM ^a	0.945	1.284	1.282	0.172
3 mM ^a	0.995	1.462	1.464	0.188
4 mM ^a	1.062	1.613	1.614	0.196
5 mM ^a	1.108	2.091	2.088	0.246

^aAspirin concentration in cholesterol solution at CMC.

Table 2. Values of various phenomenological coefficients in situation (ii) for different concentrations of aspirin

	$L_{11} \times 10^{12}$ ($m^5 N^{-1} s^{-1}$)	$L_{12} \times 10^{10}$ ($m^3 A J^{-1}$)	$L_{21} \times 10^{10}$ ($m^3 A J^{-1}$)	$L_{22} \times 10^4$ ($A V^{-1}$)
30 nM (cholesterol)	0.307	0.237	0.236	0.061
1 mM ^a	0.391	0.355	0.356	0.114
2 mM ^a	0.462	0.438	0.435	0.120
3 mM ^a	0.520	0.528	0.527	0.130
4 mM ^a	0.601	0.643	0.640	0.138
5 mM ^a	0.651	0.712	0.714	0.142

^aAspirin concentration in cholesterol solution at CMC.

Table 3. Values of various resistance coefficients in situation (i) for different concentrations of aspirin

	$R_{11}^T \times 10^{-12}$ ($m^5 N s$)	$R_{12}^T \times 10^{-6}$ ($m^{-3} A^{-1} J$)	$R_{21}^T \times 10^{-6}$ ($m^{-3} A^{-1} J$)	$R_{22}^T \times 10^{-4}$ ($A^{-1} V$)
Pure water	0.7395	7.5886	7.5886	3.684
30 nM (cholesterol)	1.2173	7.9360	7.9836	7.757
1 mM ^a	1.1246	7.9270	7.9270	6.178
2 mM ^a	1.0592	7.8952	7.9076	5.8198
3 mM ^a	1.0061	7.8353	7.8246	5.3252
4 mM ^a	0.9427	7.7636	7.7588	5.1084
5 mM ^a	0.9039	7.6727	7.6837	4.0715

^aConcentration of aspirin in cholesterol solution at CMC.

Table 4. Values of various resistance coefficients in situation (ii) for different concentrations of aspirin

	$R_{11}^\Psi \times 10^{-12}$ ($m^5 N s$)	$R_{12}^\Psi \times 10^{-6}$ ($m^{-3} A^{-1} J$)	$R_{21}^\Psi \times 10^{-6}$ ($m^{-3} A^{-1} J$)	$R_{22}^\Psi \times 10^{-4}$ ($A^{-1} V$)
30 nM (cholesterol)	3.2583	12.60589	12.6593	16.3983
1 mM ^a	2.5582	7.9889	7.9665	8.7744
2 mM ^a	2.1652	7.8490	7.9031	8.3361
3 mM ^a	1.9238	7.7990	7.8138	7.6954
4 mM ^a	1.6647	7.7204	7.7566	7.2499
5 mM ^a	1.5369	7.7280	7.7063	7.0461

^aConcentration of aspirin in cholesterol solution at CMC.

ements, i.e. sintered glass membrane and one unit of cholesterol liquid membranes and in situation (ii), we consider three membranes elements, i.e. sintered glass membrane and two unit of cholesterol liquid membranes. With these considerations we can recast eq. (5) for situation (i)

$$R_{ik}^T = R_{ik}^G + R_{ik}^C \quad (12)$$

and for situation (ii)

$$R_{ik}^* = R_{ik}^G + 2R_{ik}^C \quad (13)$$

In eqs. (12) and (13) superscripts *C*, *G*, *T* and * denote cholesterol liquid membrane, sintered glass membrane, series membrane in situation (i) and series membrane in situation (ii) respectively. The value of R_{ik}^C corresponding to liquid membranes alone have been evaluated from eq. (12) in situation (i) and from eq. (13) in situation (ii) are recorded in Tables 5 and 6 respectively. From Table 1 it can be seen that except for pure water the value of conductance coefficients L_{ik} increase with increase in concentration of aspirin in the solution of cholesterol in situation (i). The concentration of the cholesterol solution was kept constant at CMC, while the aspirin concentration was increased from 1 mM to 5 mM in the solution. A similar trend is obvious from Table 2 in situation (ii).

Table 5. Values of various resistance coefficients in situation (i) estimated from eq. (12) for different concentrations of aspirin

	$R_{11}^C \times 10^{-12}$ ($m^5 N s$)	$R_{12}^C \times 10^{-6}$ ($m^{-3} A^{-1} J$)	$R_{21}^C \times 10^{-6}$ ($m^{-3} A^{-1} J$)	$R_{22}^C \times 10^{-4}$ ($A^{-1} V$)
30 nM (cholesterol)	0.4778	0.3474	0.3950	4.078
1 mM ^a	0.3851	0.3384	0.3384	2.494
2 mM ^a	0.3197	0.3066	0.3190	2.1358
3 mM ^a	0.2666	0.2467	0.2360	1.6412
4 mM ^a	0.2032	0.1750	0.1702	1.4244
5 mM ^a	0.1664	0.0841	0.0951	0.3875

^aConcentration of aspirin in cholesterol solution at CMC.

Table 6. Values of various resistance coefficients in situation (ii) estimated from eq. (13) for different concentrations of aspirin

	$R_{11}^C \times 10^{-12}$ ($m^5 N s$)	$R_{12}^C \times 10^{-6}$ ($m^{-3} A^{-1} J$)	$R_{21}^C \times 10^{-6}$ ($m^{-3} A^{-1} J$)	$R_{22}^C \times 10^{-4}$ ($A^{-1} V$)
30 nM (cholesterol)	2.5188	5.0172	5.0707	12.7142
1 mM ^a	1.8187	0.4002	0.3779	5.0904
2 mM ^a	1.4257	0.2604	0.3145	4.6521
3 mM ^a	1.9842	0.2104	0.2252	4.0114
4 mM ^a	0.9252	0.1318	0.1680	3.5659
5 mM ^a	0.7974	0.1394	0.1177	3.3621

^aConcentration of aspirin in cholesterol solution at CMC.

The increase in flow rate of water either applying pressure difference or electrical potential difference across the liquid membranes generated by cholesterol in presence of aspirin can be attributed to morphological change in membrane organization at the interface. This can be

rationalized in terms of the fact that cholesterol is largely hydrophobic molecule. The only polar group in cholesterol is 3β-hydroxyl moiety (Fig. 1a) the remainder of the molecule is hydrophobic which comprises of a planer tetra cyclic fused sterol rings and flexible isooctyl hydrocarbon tail. The 3β-hydroxyl moiety of cholesterol gives the molecule its amphiphilic character. This makes cholesterol to generate membrane at the supporting membrane interface. At CMC of cholesterol the entire surface of supporting membrane interface is covered. At this stage the flow coefficients should not alter^{4,5,7}. When aspirin is added in cholesterol solution.

The coefficients L_{ik} (conductance coefficients) show increasing trend. This can be visualized either cholesterol layer membrane de-adsorbed at the interface providing more area to flow or cholesterol molecules changes its physical properties. The later reason appears more plausible. It has been hinted elsewhere that the inflexible and near planer steroid ring in cholesterol tends to disrupt the tight acyl chain packing (Fig. 1b)^{19,20}.

Fig. 1a. Cholesterol structure with distinguishable three parts and hydrophilic moiety 3β-hydroxyl group near the interface.

Fig. 1b. Orientation of cholesterol molecule near the interface in presence of aspirin.

To understand the coupled transport behavior of aspirin in cholesterol solution the values of degree of coupling ' q ' corresponding to liquid membranes alone (Tables 5 and 6) have been calculated from the following eq. (14).

$$q^c = -R_{12}^C \text{ (or } R_{21}^C) / \sqrt{R_{11}^C R_{22}^C} \quad (14)$$

The values thus estimated are recorded in Table 7 and plotted in Figs. 2 and 3. It can be seen from Tables 5 and 6 the values of R_{ik}^c for cholesterol liquid membrane suddenly decreases as the concentration of aspirin increases

beyond 3 mM to 5 mM (Table 7). These findings further attest the fact that the organization of cholesterol molecule at the supporting membrane water interface attains constancy of dynamic equilibrium as the concentration of aspirin reaches ≈ 3 mM in the dispersion. It has been hinted elsewhere²¹ that the 3β -hydroxyl group in cholesterol form hydrogen bonding with cholesterol molecules themselves at the interface and also with water molecules. This activity restricts the motion of cholesterol molecules at the interfaces. The plausible reason to this effect is that

Fig. 2. Dependence of degree of coupling ' q ' with concentration of aspirin in cholesterol solution at CMC in situation (i).

Fig. 3. Dependence of degree of coupling ' q ' with concentration of aspirin in cholesterol solution at CMC in situation (ii).

in the dispersion. However, the values of q^c do not decrease appreciably with increase in aspirin concentration

in presence of aspirin the rigid sterol ring of cholesterol molecules and alkyl chain transform organization and

Table 7. Dependence of degree of coupling, q , on concentration of aspirin

Concentration	$q^T \times 10^2$	$q^* \times 10^2$
	Situation (i) data used from Table 5	Situation (ii) data used from Table 6
30 nM ^a	0.2489	0.8865
1 nM ^a	0.3453	0.1315
2 nM ^a	0.3711	0.1011
3 nM ^a	0.3729	0.09653
4 nM ^a	0.3253	0.07256
5 nM ^a	0.3312	0.08514

^aConcentration of aspirin in cholesterol solution at CMC.

function at the interface (Fig. 1). Alternatively, one can speculate the cholesterol molecules alone occupy greater area at interface and are thus responsible for low permeability. On addition of aspirin some of the molecules of cholesterol are monohydrated near the interface due to hydrogen bonding^{21,22} and provide more space for permeability of water. Obviously, more free space is available in fluid cholesterol molecules which are in metastable state. These findings lend support to the fact that aspirin is capable to reduce the spontaneous assembly of cholesterol at the interface.

Conclusions

The electroosmotic transport studies across liquid membranes generated by cholesterol at CMC (30 nM) in presence of aspirin at five concentration (1 mM to 5 mM) have been studied. The phenomenological coefficients show increasing trend with increase in aspirin concentration. The resistance coefficients, however, decrease with increase in aspirin concentration. This has been rationalized in terms of possible hydrogen bonding with cholesterol-cholesterol molecules and cholesterol-water molecules at the interface which restricts the motion of cholesterol molecules at the interface. Also, the expected configurational change in cholesterol in presence of aspirin allows high permeability. The results thus obtained corroborate the fact that aspirin acts as anticoagulant which restricts the spontaneous assembly of cholesterol.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry for providing necessary facilities. One of us (MS) is grateful to UGC-DSA program for financial assistance.

References

1. R. E. Kesting, "Synthetic Polymeric Membranes", McGraw Hill Book Co., New York, 1971.
2. R. E. Kesting, W. J. Subcasky and J. D. Paton, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1968, **28**, 156.
3. H. T. Tien, "Bilayer Lipid Membranes, Theory and Practice", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1974.
4. R. C. Srivastava and R. P. S. Jakhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 1457.
5. A. K. Jain and R. K. Srivastava, *J. Membrane Sci.*, 1990, **51**, 337.
6. A. K. Jain and R. K. Srivastava, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 1991, **145**, 447.
7. R. C. Srivastava and A. N. Nagappa, "Surface activity in Drug action", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2005; R. C. Srivastava and R. P. Rastogi, "Transport Mediated by Electrified Interfaces", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2003.
8. J. M. Orten and O. W. Neuhaus, "Biochemistry", 8th ed., The C. V. Mosby Company, Sant Louis, 1970.
9. G. S. Joshi, J. C. Burnett and D. J. Abraham, in "Burger's Medicinal chemistry and Drug Discovery", 6th ed., 'Vol. 3, eds. D. J. Abraham, John Willey and Sons, Inc, New Jersey, 2003.
10. A. T. Chan, S. Ogina and C. S. Fuchs, *N. Engl. J. Med.*, 2007, **356**, 2131.
11. R. M. Epand, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 2003, **1610**, 155.
12. R. G. Anderson and K. Jacobson, *Science*, 2002, **1821**, 296.
13. I. Prigogine, "Introduction to the thermodynamics of irreversible process", Wiley, New York, 1968.
14. A. Katchalsky and P. F. Curran, "Non-equilibrium Thermodynamics in Biophysics", Harvard University Press, Cambridge, 1965.
15. R. P. Rastogi, "Non-equilibrium Thermodynamics, Physical Chemistry", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2008.
16. O. Kedam and A. Katchalsky, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, **57**, 1941.
17. H. T. Tien, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **71**, 3395.
18. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans Green, London, 1956.
19. T. J. Pucadyil and A. Chattopadhyay, *Prog. Lipid. Res.*, 2006, **45**, 295.
20. L. A. Estroff and A. D. Hamilton, *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 1201.
21. D. M. Small, "The Physical Chemistry of Lipids", Plenum Press, New York, 1988.
22. J. M. Boggs, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1987, **906**, 353.